

In memoriam

Professor Angel Yordanov Kunov, DSc (May 15, 1941 – June 28, 2023)

On June 28, 2023, Professor Angel Kunov, DSc, a highly respected and longtime scientist at the Geological Institute of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, and an outstanding Bulgarian researcher in magmatism, metasomatism and mineral resources, with a particular interest in their geochemistry, mineralogy and petrology, passed away at the age of 82. In our deepest sympathies, we mourn the passing of an esteemed colleague, who dedicated his entire career to the field of geology.

Angel Kunov was born on May 15, 1941, in the town of Vratsa (NW Bulgaria) and grew up in the modest family of Yordan and Zorka Kunovi, with two younger sisters who later became famous journalists. After graduating from the Second High School in Vratsa, Angel Kunov graduated from Sofia University (Faculty of Biology, Geology and Geography, 1961–1966) in geology (geochemistry) as a graduate of Acad. Ivan Kostov. After graduation, he worked for five years as a geologist (team leader) at the State Enterprise for Geological Studies and a few months at the Technical Development Base – Vladya (Sofia). The main part of Angel Kunov's professional life, starting from December 12, 1971, was spent at the Geological Institute, where he retired in 2010. His early career was spent under the guidance of Assoc. Prof. Elena Dimitrova.

At the Geological Institute, Angel Kunov developed a remarkable scientific career, initially as a geochemist (1971–1976) and later moving through the positions of Research Assistant (1976–1994), Associate Professor (1994–2006) and Full Professor (2006–2010). He defended his PhD thesis in 1986. In 2002, Angel Kunov defended his DSc thesis “En-

dogene-supergene metasomatic systems of epithermal ore deposits and occurrences of acid-sulfate and adularia-sericite type (cases from Bulgaria)”. Of note are his specializations in 1977 at the Institute of the Earth's crusts – Irkutsk, and the Institute of Geology of Ore Deposits, Petrography, Mineralogy and Geochemistry (IGEM) of the Russian Academy of Sciences. From 1987 to 1988, Angel Kunov participated with geologists of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences in the third stage of the Bulgarian-Cuban geological expedition of the province of Santa Clara (Cuba), where he co-investigated ore deposits and occurrences. Also worth noting is his academic

activity (1995–1997), which comprises lectures and exercises in Wall-Rock Alterations for geologists at Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”, as well as lectures and postgraduate courses for geologists and prospectors at the University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”, Sofia.

Professor Angel Kunov was the head and consultant of graduates and doctoral students. During his career, he worked with a number of colleagues from different fields of geology. His mature years saw him pay special attention to younger geologists and offer guidance and support, being sincere, dedicated, and committed without seeking recognition. Professor Kunov authored numerous expert opinions and reports, as well as article, book and monograph reviews and evaluations of theses and scientific competitions. His involvement in various scientific councils, examination committees, and juries was extensive. He was a member of the Bulgarian Geological Society, Bulgarian Mineralogical Society and the European Association for the Conservation of Geological Heritage (ProGeo).

Professor Angel Kunov authored and coauthored more than 130 original research articles, 35 popular articles, and several books. In his early years, he worked on the petrology of the Lower Paleozoic rocks in the Western Balkan Mts. Among his numerous theoretical and applied contributions are those in geochemistry, mineralogy, petrology and the mineral resources. In both individual and collective settings (either as a leader or participant), he discovered metallic and non-metallic deposits and occurrences, as well as 35 new minerals and varieties for Bulgaria, and added to the knowledge about many geological sites. Special mention should be made of the collective monograph *The Metasomatic Secondary Quartzite Formation in Bulgaria* (2007), in which he was a leading researcher. Nationally and internationally, this work was well received. His works in studying the unique prehistoric rock paint-

ings in Magura Cave in NW Bulgaria is fascinating. The collective monograph *The Earth – The Restless Planet* (2008), edited by him, presented geological science to the Bulgarian public in an accessible manner. Professor Kunov’s books *In the Cradle of Gaia* (2000), *Contemplations* (2016), and *Path with the Caresses of the Sublime* (2020) reveal him not only as a geologist, but also as a philosopher, publicist, and romantic. Through his numerous talks in libraries, museums and schools, as well as his appearances on the radio and television, he has given much publicity to geology.

In Vratsa, his hometown, Professor Kunov continued to engage in active social activities after retiring. It is he who initiated and created the “Rock Rainbow” geological exhibition at the Regional History Museum of Vratsa. He donated many geological samples to the “Hristo Botev” High School in Vratsa and helped create a new geography study room. In his role on the “Memory of Vratsa” Committee, he developed a number of helpful local history projects for the community, including the building of the Memorial to the victims of the Anglo-American bombing and the dead residents of Vratsa during World War II, as well as the Memorial to flood victims of May 1, 1966. Vratsa declared Angel Kunov an honorary citizen in 2009 and named him “Revival Leader of the Year” in 2014.

Angel Kunov devoted much love to Nature and Man throughout his life and professional career. He was not only a distinguished scientist, but a great personality and publicist, with an unrelenting spirit of inquiry and research persistence, always maintaining a noticeable modesty and collegiality. In his life, his faithful companion was Milena until her death, with whom he had three children, four grandchildren and one great-granddaughter. In this memento, we wish to express our deepest sympathies to Angel Kunov’s family. He was a wonderful man and friend, and will be greatly missed.

Lubomir Metodiev

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